

#ALPHALOOP_V3 by Adelin Schweitzer

Source: [The Quietus](#)

Date: *Published 5 November 2019*

Title: *Hallucinogenic Empathetic Entertainment: L.E.V Matadero Reviewed*

Excerpt: "*#ALPHALOOP is a disorienting 'techno-shamanism' project by French artist Adelin Schweitzer. Participants are guided on a journey that blurs the boundaries between reality and virtual perception, prompting them to rethink their relationship with technology.*"

Source: [Fisheye Immersive](#)

Date: **13 December 2024**

Title: *Virtual Reality: Is a DIY Creation Possible?*

Excerpt: "With *Le Test Sutherland*, artist Adelin Schweitzer proposes an immersive configuration of a particular kind that questions the overly predictable functional principles of current virtualized fictions by rethinking the technical setup of the VR/AR headset itself. Presented as part of *Altered States* and the Biennale Chroniques opening, this experience is driven by DIY principles that place the work far from traditional virtualized devices. Schweitzer even developed a prototype headset called BUD (Black Up Display) intended to 'disrupt the immersion industry and shift the balance of power in XR headsets.' Participants undertake cognitive micro-workshops that challenge touch, balance, and perception, transforming conventional expectations of immersive VR."

Source: [Fisheye Immersive](#)

Date: *13 March 2024*

Type: Art & Photography Magazine

Title: *Adelin Schweitzer: An Ode to Altered, Rather than Augmented, Reality?*

Excerpt: "*Adelin Schweitzer employs technological tools to critique their applications in XR works that interrogate Californian ideology. His creations encourage reflection on our reliance on immersive technologies and their effects on our perception of reality.*"